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Abolition of The Exequatur Procedure in Civil and Commercial Matters in Accordance with Regulation 805/2004 of The European Union

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Abstract

The exequatur procedure is a mechanism of international civil and commercial procedural law according to which a foreign enforceable title must be declared enforceable in the Member State in which enforcement is sought before it can be subject to enforcement. Given the fact that it is indeed illogical to grant enforceability and refuse recognition of a foreign enforceable title, especially if it concerns an uncontested claim (which can more can less!!!), the civil and commercial law of the European Union is fighting for the abolition of exequatur. This is because exequatur is an intermediate procedure, between the cognizance procedure for the adoption of a judgment and the enforcement procedure, which slows down the free movement of judgements in the European Union. The abolition of the exequatur procedure deserves full approval because in this way the risk of late settlement of creditors' claims is reduced, and this improves the liquidity of small and medium-sized enterprises in the European Union if they have outstanding but overdue claims as creditors. It is for this reason that the subject of analysis of this paper are the steps that the civil and commercial procedural law of the European Union has taken to eliminate exequatur, as well as the benefits for small and medium-sized enterprises from the elimination of exequatur, primarily in terms of faster payment of claims.

Keywords: European Union law, national enforcement titles, exequatur procedure, European enforcement order, small and medium-sized enterprises

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I. Introduction

The European Enforcement Order for Uncontested Claims as a legal institute of the civil and commercial procedural law of the EU was created by Regulation (EC) No. 805/2004 of the European Parliament and of the European Council with the aim of eliminating the *exequatur* procedure, as an intermediate procedure, between the cognizance procedure for the adoption of the judgment and the enforcement procedure.

The reason for the introduction of the European Enforcement Order for Uncontested Claims should be sought in the need to resolve the problems in the cross-border enforcement of judgments, the proper functioning of the internal market and the reduction of the risk of late settlement of creditors' claims. (Gjorgieva & Stoileva, 2014)

With the help of Regulation 805/2004, the judgement is confirmed as a European Enforcement Order for Uncontested Claims in the Member State from which it originates, and is enforceable in the Member States of the European Union, without the need for the debtor to obtain a judgement for enforcement in the Member State of enforcement or to oppose its recognition.

The abolition of *exequatur* represents a new functional rule in the field of European enforcement procedural law. (van der Grinten & van der Velden, 2006)

The basic hypothesis of this paper is that Regulation 805/2004 eliminates *exequatur* without sufficient harmonization of civil and commercial procedural law of the European Union, without creating a community European enforcement procedure and without exclusive application of minimum standards in the Member States of the European Union. Undoubtedly, certificate of European Enforcement Order for uncontested claims can only be obtained by judgments that are in favor of uncontested or uncontested monetary claims, and not for disputed and/or non-monetary claims.

The abolition of the *exequatur* procedure is an ideological idea of the European legislator that is balanced with concentrated control over the procedure for making a judgment and increasing the procedural guarantees for a fair trial of the debtor as a party to the procedure.

The complete elimination of the *exequatur* procedure is required by the Treaty of Amsterdam and the Treaty of Lisbon on the establishment of the European Union because it is an indisputable fact that the *exequatur* procedure is an "intermediate procedure between the cognizance procedure for making a judgment and the enforcement procedure" (Portmann, 2007) which hinders the "fifth freedom of the European Union market" - the free movement of judgments. As such, the *exequatur* procedure slows down the enforcement of judgement and is an obstacle to the rapid realization of undisputed claims of creditors, which can negatively affect the liquidity of small and medium-sized enterprises in the Member States of the European Union.

The topic of the abolition of *exequatur* is the focus of many scientific papers. The most important of these are the doctoral dissertation of Portmann Frederike (Regulation (EC) 805/2004 creating a European Enforcement Order for uncontested claims and its consequences for debtor protection published in 2007 and the doctoral dissertation of Vittorio Pozzi (European Enforcement Titles: Problems and Prospects) published in 2007.

II. Methods

From a methodological point of view, the creation of the European Enforcement Order for uncontested claims and the abolition of *exequatur* are influenced by two variables: a) the need for greater efficiency of European procedures and b) procedural guarantees for a fair trial.

Throughout the paper, the method of analysis and synthesis was used as the basic method.

The normative method was used to analyze the positive provisions of Regulation 805/2004 in order to address the need to amend some of its solutions, *de lege ferenda*.

The historical method was used to understand the time circumstances and the phase of development of the civil procedural law of the European Union when the European Enforcement

Order for uncontested claims was created and when exequatur was abolished for uncontested claims.

The comparative method was used to compare the provisions on the abolition of exequatur of Regulation 805/2004 with some other European regulations that abolish exequatur, with the aim of their mutual improvement and perfection.

III. Discussion and Results

1. Steps of the European Union's Civil Procedural Law Towards a Europe Without Exequatur

In Community law, five steps (Malatesta, 2008) have been taken towards a "Europe without exequatur", namely 1) the transformation of the Brussels Convention into Regulation 44/2001, which simplified the procedure for recognition and enforcement of judgments³, 2) Regulation 2201/2003, which abolished the exequatur procedure, first of all for judgments in family disputes, 3) Regulations 805/2004 and 1896/2006, which require the abolition of exequatur in the area of uncontested claims, 4) Regulation 4/2009⁴ which requires its complete elimination in the area of contested claims as well and 5) Regulation 1215/2012, which definitively abolishes the exequatur procedure in the area of uncontested and contested claims.

2. Abolition of the Exequatur Procedure for Undisputed Claims in Accordance with the Legal Regime of Regulation 805/2004

Regulation 805/2004 provides that if the minimum standards of the cognizance procedure in the Member State of origin of the judgment are respected, the creditor in the Member State of enforcement does not need to obtain a judgement for the enforcement of a confirmed European Enforcement Order which relates to an uncontested claim.

This avoids the possible three-stage process⁵ of the exequatur procedure under the mechanism of Regulation 44/2001 by transferring control of the judgment from the Member State of enforcement to the Member State of origin (the home advantage principle of the creditor), with exceptions.

An exception to this rule exists when the debtor is a consumer, because then the certificate for a European Enforcement Order relating to an uncontested claim can only be issued by a court or tribunal of the European Union Member State in which the consumer is domiciled.

"The method of controlling the national enforcement title only in the Member State of its origin is a strength, but at the same time a weakness of the overall system of Regulation 805/2004". (Pozzi, 2007) This allows a confirmed European enforcement title that relates to an uncontested claim to be directly and under the same conditions enforced in any Member State of the European Union, and not only in the Member State where the creditor has obtained the enforcement title, which eliminates the public order of the Member State of enforcement as a prerequisite for the recognition and enforcement of the national enforcement title. With this, Regulation 805/2004 requires the abolition of exequatur around uncontested claims throughout the European Community.

³ If a comparison is made between Article 34 of the Brussels Convention and Article 41 of Regulation 44/2001, it can be noted that the latter facilitates the recognition and enforcement of decisions much more, because according to it, the court does not examine the circumstances that may be a reason for refusing recognition.

⁴ The abolition of exequatur is also the basic idea of Regulation 4/2009 when it comes to disputed claims. It introduces an alternative measure to ensure the rights of the defendant by creating a posteriori review procedure. It abolishes exequatur by unifying the rules on applicable law and protecting the rights of the defense through a special review procedure that applies after the decision has been issued.

⁵ The exequatur procedure means that the foreign title must be declared enforceable in the Member State in which enforcement is sought before it can be enforced. The exequatur procedure under Regulation 44/2001 consists of three stages. The first stage begins with the creditor filing an ex-parte application for enforcement, the second stage begins if an appeal is lodged against the enforcement decision and the third stage begins with the lodging of an appeal against the second-instance decision.

Reasons for eliminating exequatur are most often the unnecessary costs and time lost in its conduct that fall on the creditor's shoulders and the principle of mutual trust, which is the foundation on which European procedural law has yet to be built.

Although the idea of abolishing exequatur deserves full approval, this procedure should not be abolished completely, for now, for several reasons. Exequatur should not be abolished solely because it represents a loss of time and greater costs for the creditor, because it is undeniable that the price of justice⁶ is different in different Member States of the European Union.

In addition, the arguments regarding the time and costs of its duration as a reason for its abolition are unconvincing. Namely, justice is often quite slow in some member states, and exequatur is not even close to being the only reason for this. At the same time, if the problem is time and costs, it seems that the measures of community law should be directed towards that, and not towards its complete elimination.

The statistical data⁷ of the European Commission Report (Hess et al., 2007) also speak in favour of this, which show that it is a very successful and fast procedure. This procedure in the first instance lasts on average from 7 days to 4 months if a complete application is submitted and very rarely, only in 1 to 5% of cases, it moves to the second instance. If an appeal is filed, the procedure lasts from 1 month to 3 years, depending on the procedural and cultural differences of the member states and the overload of the courts. The study shows that in 90 to 100% of cases the exequatur procedure ends successfully.

The abolition of exequatur is directly and directly in conflict with the national interest of the Member State of enforcement and the defence of the interests of the debtor in the procedure, which is why even some proceduralists take the position that its complete elimination would be a real "leap in the dark of Community law" if the principle of mutual trust in European judicial procedural systems is not guaranteed. This principle does not in itself guarantee that a judgment in the Member State of origin meets all the conditions for being universally enforceable.

Namely, there is a lack of confidence in the ability to properly issue a certificate for a European enforcement order that is based on an undisputed claim, since the issuance of the certificate may lead to arbitrariness and abuse of power by national judicial authorities.

For example, they may deliberately refuse to issue the certificate, something against which the parties *de iure* have no legal remedy.

This should be resolved either by creating a supranational, Community control body⁸ or by treating national courts as European courts⁹, which is the essence of the principle of mutual trust between courts. (Kenneth, 2000)

⁶ It is mentioned that an enforcement procedure in England is five times more expensive than the same one in Spain.

⁷ It is difficult to provide precise data on the actual applicability of the exequatur procedure because there is no central system for collecting statistical data in the European Union. However, some information can be obtained from the Ministries of Justice of the Member States. The rules on recognition and enforcement under Regulation 44/2001 vary considerably, from 10 declarations in Portugal in 2004, to a maximum of 420 in Luxembourg, and a maximum of 301 declarations in the Landgericht Traunstein in Germany.

⁸ In order to abolish exequatur, it is necessary for citizens to be able to truly trust in the principle of mutual trust, which means that they have the same real opportunity to seek liability from the courts of other Member States as they do before their own courts, with the possibility of also seeking compensation from the court that has made an incorrect decision for the damage suffered. For this reason, it is considered that the confirmation of the European Enforcement Order for uncontested claims should be issued in the Member State of origin by EC courts. This type of courts is required to be present and exist in all Member States. It is considered that only such courts would ensure real control over the decisions and that they would, through practice, perfect European confirmation according to the mechanism of Regulation 805/2004. Thus, the European procedure for the confirmation of the national as a European Enforcement Order for uncontested claims would not be reduced to a mere formality.

⁹ If national courts were to function as European courts, foreign judgments given in a Member State would enjoy the status of judgments given at home and would enter into force in the same way without formalities and without prior proceedings or accompanying formalities.

Trust between Member States should be built by reducing the reasons for doubting the reliability of the national legal systems of the Member States. The price that Community law must pay for the hasty abolition of exequatur must in no case be a violation of the constitutional rights and fundamental human rights of the debtor in the cognizance procedure for issuing the judgment. In this regard, the question arises whether the minimum standards of Regulation 805/2004 for the protection of the debtor's rights are sufficient due to the lack of unification of European civil procedural law in cognizance proceedings in which the judgment is rendered.

Currently, the minimum standards are too vague and general, which de facto may be in the creditor's favour, since he chooses the judicial body and the procedural law under which the procedure will be conducted, which opens the possibility for him to choose the most favourable for himself.¹⁰

The other reason arises from the non-mandatory nature of their application and the fact that over 50% of applications for European validation are rejected due to non-compliance with the minimum standards.

At the same time, we should not forget the fact that the exequatur procedure is an alternative European procedure that leaves the creditor the opportunity, if he fails to settle his claim under the mechanism of Regulation 805/2004, to take procedural actions under Regulation 44/2001, which *in ultima linea* is also his *ius variandi*. (Zilinsky, 2005)

"The procedures under Regulations 44/2001 and 805/2004 are alternative, non-exclusive European procedures" (Pozzi, 2007) according to which the creditor can simultaneously file a request for enforcement, first in the home country under Regulation 805/2004, and then abroad under Regulation 44/2001.

In the procedural literature, there are arguments pro et contra for this. It is considered inadvisable to conduct them in parallel due to the lack of a legal interest of the creditor in this and due to the possibility of making contradictory judgements upon their completion due to the differences that they foresee as obstacles to enforcement. Here, first, the institute of public order is meant. However, it is generally accepted that, if the creditor fails in the exequatur procedure at first instance, he can initiate a procedure under Regulation 805/2004.

The absence of a universal Community enforcement procedure is the most important reason why exequatur should not be completely abolished, because it opens the danger that the debtor will defend himself before a foreign court, which undoubtedly leads to a high degree of uncertainty in a situation where there is no harmonisation in enforcement. (Hess, 2005) It can be concluded that the complete abolition of exequatur as a new step in European civil procedural law aimed pro future should come gradually through a true approximation of European civil and enforcement law by guaranteeing the rights of the parties at a higher level and through the integration of judicial systems throughout the European Community. (Porcelli, 2008)

3. Similarities and Differences Between the European Enforcement Order for Uncontested Claims and Other European Union Enforcement Orders That Abolish Exequatur

The mechanism of Regulation 805/2004 is conceived as a mechanism that has yet to be expanded and to abolish exequatur in all possible places. "As its ideological successors, the European Payment Order, which applies primarily to commercial litigation, and the European Enforcement Order in Small Claims Procedure, which applies primarily to consumer litigation, were created." An evolution vis-à-vis the mechanism of Regulation 805/2004 is the mechanism of Regulation 1215/12, which abolished the mechanism of Regulation 44/2001.

The following amendments to the exequatur procedure are considered desirable:

¹⁰ Otherwise, the absence of uniform legal rules on conflict of laws and harmonized legal procedures for the defense of the debtor together with a uniform procedure for service are strong obstacles to the possibility of enforcing the decision. Although the solution cannot be unified for all cases, there must nevertheless be some safeguards to ensure the rights of the debtor in cross-border cases.

- amendment of Annex 5 to Regulation 44/2001 and its alignment with Regulations 805/2004 and 1896/2006
- deletion of Article 40 of Regulation 44/2001
- further simplification of the procedure. (Kramer, 2008)

3.1 The Relationship Between the European Enforcement Order for Uncontested Claims and the European Payment Order from the Perspective of the Abolition of Exequatur

The European order for payment as a one-step process is an evolution vis-à-vis the European Enforcement Order for Uncontested Claims in the civil procedural law of the European Union. (Pozzi, 2007; Lupoi, 2008; Delcasso, 2008; Commission of the European Communities, 2002) Although both legal institutions are based on the same ideological basis, the abolition of exequatur as an intermediate procedure, they do so in completely different ways. In both enforcement orders, exequatur is circumvented by means of minimum standards.¹¹ The difference is that according to Regulation 805/2004, the minimum standards are treated as a prerequisite for issuing a certificate for a European Enforcement Order for Uncontested Claims and regulate the delivery of the document initiating the procedure in the Member State of origin, unlike the mechanism of Regulation 1896/2006, where they refer to the delivery in the Member State of enforcement of the already received European order for payment and are a prerequisite that the debtor has been notified of the European order for payment and its enforcement in a timely manner.

The European Enforcement Order for Uncontested Claims aims at indirect harmonisation, through the Europeanisation of the effect of judgements, unlike the European Payment Order which establishes a single procedure common to all Member States, which creates the European Payment Order as an alternative to the national one.

The procedure for obtaining a European Payment Order itself is a shortened procedure, without an oral hearing, which avoids the risk of the creditor engaging in unknown foreign civil court proceedings.

The European Enforcement Order for Uncontested Claims and the European Payment Order are enforcement titles of the European Union which are obtained in alternative automated, European procedures which are mutually exclusive, with the European payment model being a special type of European Enforcement Order for Uncontested Claims aimed pro future.

Moreover, the European Payment Order is a much bolder instrument because it introduces a new model of judgements following the example of the Austrian Mahnverfahren and the Portuguese De injunção, which differs from the European Enforcement Order for Uncontested Claims, which also applies to judgements after the judgment has been challenged.

As previously stated, the enforcement orders of Regulations 805/2004 and 1896/2006 play an important role in the harmonisation of the civil procedural law of the European Union, but from different aspects.

The main difference is the fact that the enforcement nature of the act created under Regulation 805/2004 does not have to have a cross-border element, but can also be applied to purely internal relations, unlike the European Payment Order, which is expressly limited to cross-border disputes.

Another difference between the procedures under Regulations 805/2004 and 1896/2006 arises from their application *ratione materiae* because the claim in the European order for

¹¹ If we compare Articles 13 and 14 of Regulation 805/2004 and Articles 13 and 14 of Regulation 1896/2006, it can be concluded that the free flow of European payment orders is ensured by prescribing minimum standards prior to the procedure for its recognition and enforcement.

payment undoubtedly tends to be of a contractual nature, unlike the European Enforcement Order for uncontested claims which is not limited to the source of the claim.¹²

The European order for payment applies only to uncontested pecuniary claims which are precisely determined and due, unlike the European Enforcement Order which applies to uncontested pecuniary claims which are determined or determinable and do not necessarily have to be due.¹³

3.2 Relationship of the European Enforcement Order for Uncontested Claims with the European Enforcement Order Obtained in the European Small Claims Procedure from the Aspect of the Abolition of Exequatur

Seven months after the introduction of the European Order for Payment procedure, Community law has introduced a new non-exclusive European procedure which offers many advantages over the procedures for the creation of a European Enforcement Order for uncontested claims and the European Order for Payment.

Unlike the mechanism of Regulation 805/2004 and following the example of Regulation 1896/2006 and Regulation 861/2007, it applies only to cross-border cases.

From the point of view of its validity *ratione materiae*, it differs from the procedure that created the European Enforcement Order for uncontested claims because cases relating to the violation of privacy or other personal rights, including defamation, disputes relating to state-owned real estate (except for actions for monetary claims) and employment law, are expressly excluded from its scope.¹⁴

The applicability of this procedure, unlike the procedure that created the European Enforcement Order for Uncontested Claims, is limited *ratione valoris*, i.e. it is applied in cross-border cases where the value of the claim, excluding interest, costs and expenses, does not exceed EUR 2,000 at the time when the competent court or tribunal receives the claim form.¹⁵

Unlike the European Enforcement Order for Uncontested Claims, which applies only to uncontested monetary claims, the judgment confirmed under the European Small Claims Procedure mechanism may be for non-monetary and monetary claims. This procedure is conducted according to the *lex fori* processus and is based on the principles of fair trial and adversarial proceedings, unlike the European Enforcement Order for Uncontested Claims procedure, which is an alternative European procedure permitted only for cases that are uncontested by the debtor and is a non-adversarial procedure. These principles should be particularly evident when the court decides to hold an oral hearing and when determining the manner of taking evidence. Unlike the mechanism of Regulation 805/2004, it does not provide for any rules on exclusive jurisdiction and puts the minimum standards for service in the background, introducing autonomous rules for service of documents by post.¹⁶

The European Small Claims Procedure introduces special rules to reduce the costs of cross-border litigation, something that is not defined by the mechanism of Regulation 805/2004 in accordance with the principles of unity, speed and equality. It is believed that its practical application would reduce the total costs of litigation by 20% or by 8 000 000 000 euros. (Kramer,

¹² Unlike Regulation 805/2004, it does not apply to claims arising from non-contractual liability, with exceptions (if they are the subject of an agreement between the parties or if there has been an acknowledgement of debt or when it comes to a debt the amount of which is determined and arises from joint ownership of real estate).

¹³ According to Article 4 of Regulation 1896/2006, the European order for payment procedure applies only to the collection of monetary claims whose value is determined, and the claim is due at the time of submitting the application for a European order for payment.

¹⁴ Article 2 of Regulation No. 861/2007.

¹⁵ The maximum limit on the value of the claim to only 2,000 euros has been highly criticized and it is believed that this threshold should be raised to 5,000 euros.

¹⁶ Article 9 of Regulation 861/2007 provides that the document shall be served by post with a receipt containing the date of receipt and the signature. If service is not possible in this manner, service may be affected in accordance with Articles 13 and 14 of Regulation 805/2004.

2008) It reduces the costs of translation and legal aid, the costs related to the duration of national litigation by introducing fixed, preclusive deadlines for the parties to undertake procedural actions and eliminates the need for mandatory representation of the parties during the procedure.

It can be concluded that several instruments have been adopted in European Union law, the main drawback of which is their contradictory content and the impossibility of their full harmonisation.

For this reason, it is no coincidence that the 2009 Stockholm Programme opens the possibility for the European Commission to introduce, pro future, a new instrument of the European Union, which will unite the European Enforcement Order for Uncontested Claims, the European Order for Payment and the European Small Claims Procedure. (Čolović, 2010)

3.3 Relationship of the European Enforcement Order for Uncontested Claims with the European Enforcement Order Obtained Under Regulation 1215/12 from the Aspect of the Abolition of Exequatur

The main objective of the European Enforcement Order under Regulation 2015/12 is to facilitate and accelerate the mutual recognition of judgements between Member States and to promote the movement of judgements through facilitated enforcement. It does this by abolishing the enforcement procedure and introducing a simplified mechanism for the recognition and enforcement of judgments of the Member States of the European Union.

The creditor under the mechanism of Regulation 2015/12 should apply for enforcement of the judgement to the court enforcing the decision together with a copy of the decision and a standard certificate from the court that issued the decision, as referred to in Article 53 of the Regulation. In practice, it is recommended that the creditor seeking enforcement submit a translation of certain documents together with the decision in case the party opposing enforcement so requests. The debtor under the operative part of the decision may oppose enforcement on the grounds set out in Article 45 of Regulation 1215/12. This simplified procedure for the abolition of the exequatur established by Regulation 2015/12 is in line with Regulation 805/2004 which for the first time abolished exequatur for uncontested claims whose value and date are determined. (Schramm, 2014) All that is required under the mechanism of Regulation 1215/12 for enforcement is a certificate known as a "European Enforcement Order" from the court that issued the decision. (Cadet, 2015)

4. The Impact of Regulation 805/2004 on Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are key elements that undoubtedly shape the European economy. They provide more than two-thirds of private-sector employment and are key to economic growth. (European Commission, 2011) The analysis of the impact of EU Regulation 805/2004 on SMEs is directly related to its adoption, which is to simplify the enforcement of uncontested commercial claims in the EU Member States. The Regulation 805/2004 stimulates a much more efficient process of cross-border debt collection by eliminating procedures such as exequatur. SMEs established in EU Member States operate in relatively complex legal systems and often face resource constraints in their day-to-day transaction enforcement.

From an SME perspective, it is of particular importance that the Regulation 805/2004 applies to uncontested claims, such as a claim where the debtor has expressly agreed to the amount of the debt through an acknowledgment or a settlement approved by a court; where the debt has not been objected in court proceedings; if, under the law of the Member State in which the litigation is brought, the debtor initially lodged an objection and then failed to appear or be represented at a court hearing, such conduct constitutes a tacit admission; or the debtor himself has expressly agreed to the claim in an authentic instrument. This treatment of uncontested claims applies in all EU member states except Denmark. However, from the perspective of intensive international trade practice, it must be emphasized that these uncontested claims do not apply if the debt originates from tax, customs, administrative obligations, bankruptcy, social security, or arbitration.

The greatest benefit to SMEs operating in international trade is that Regulation 805/2004 provides a simplified mechanism for enforcing uncontested claims without the need for additional legal proceedings in the Member State of Enforcement. The reduced time and costs associated with debt collection positively impact on the allocation of resources and capacities. The degree of facilitation of cross-border enforcement of uncontested claims established by the Regulation 805/2004 from the perspective of SMEs is generally assessed as easier. The very abolition of the *exequatur* has contributed to making enforcement easier. However, it is important to emphasize that law enforcement is not always unproblematic, even in such circumstances. It depends on categorizing the enforced claim and in which Member State. Not all member states have adequate enforcement legislation, which complicates implementation in some ways. In principle, the duration of the enforcement process under the Regulation 805/2004 is assessed as shorter compared to the enforcement process regulated in other EU acts, such as the Brussels I Regulation and the Brussels I *bis* Regulation. (von Hein et al., 2016)

Enforcement proceedings traditionally involve significant legal and administrative costs. Regulation 805/2004 minimizes these costs by eliminating the *exequatur*, making it a cost-effective solution for SMEs seeking to collect debts from international trade transactions. The general perception is that it is not necessary to obtain equal status in the Member State in which enforcement is to be carried out, as was required before the adoption of the Regulation 805/2004, and as a result, the costs of cross-border enforcement are reduced. The additional costs that arise in cross-border enforcement proceedings are related to translation costs and costs arising from the cross-border delivery of documents. Even in cases where legal representation is not mandatory, cross-border proceedings often involve attorneys and such legal costs for SMEs are significant. About the court procedure, the costs arising from the application of the procedure provided for in the EEA Regulation may be included in the total fee of the procedure at the very beginning, and some Member States charge a relatively small fee after the judgment has been delivered.

The Regulation 805/2004 has a significant impact on improving the liquidity of SMEs by simplifying cross-border debt collection within the EU. By allowing judgments on uncontested claims to be enforced across Member States without cross-border proceedings, the Regulation reduces the time and legal costs of recovering late payments from foreign debtors. This accelerated access to outstanding funds improves cash flow security, enabling SMEs to reinvest in operations, meet financial obligations, and reduce dependence on external financing. In essence, the Regulation strengthens SMEs' financial stability and competitiveness in the internal market. The European Parliament has acknowledged that late payments directly affect liquidity and cash flow predictability, increasing working capital needs and threatening competitiveness, especially for SMEs. In this regard, the European Parliament has committed to combating late payments in commercial transactions and highlights ongoing efforts to improve payment practices and support the liquidity of SMEs. (European Commission, 2023)

The Regulation 805/2004 strictly enforces the establishment of unified standards within the EU internal market, thus providing SMEs with greater legal certainty. Legal predictability in international trade is a key prerequisite for concluding contracts and engaging in international trade transactions with partners operating in other EU Member States. The European legislator always strives to reduce the burden on SMEs when structuring legal norms that have an intensive commercial effect.

The limited scope represents a serious disadvantage created for SMEs. The Regulation 805/2004 only applies to uncontested claims, and in cases where the debtor contests the claim, SMEs must resort to traditional enforcement procedures, which can be more expensive. Additionally, SMEs as claimants face uncertainty regarding the nature and qualification of the debt as uncontested. The limited use of Regulation 805/2004, in addition to its undeniable drawbacks, is also influenced by the parallel application of the Brussels I *bis* Regulation after the abolition of *exequatur*.

Despite its benefits, European SMEs are still characterized by reduced awareness and limited application of the mechanism created by the Regulation 805/2004. Many SMEs may not be fully informed about the availability and benefits, leading to underutilizing this mechanism.

The degree of low awareness of the benefits results from the low frequency of application. Low awareness is also a result of a lack of specific legal training. A certain inertia exists due to the tendency to prefer legal tools with which they are already familiar, rather than experimenting with new ones. However, practitioners specializing in international civil and commercial law are familiar with the Regulation and take advantage of its advantages. (von Hein et al., 2016) Addressing the responsibility for the relatively low awareness of the benefits of the Regulation 805/2004 lies in the principle of subsidiarity, which means that both Member States and the Commission share the responsibility for raising awareness among SMEs. All these initiatives aim to improve the competitiveness of SMEs through improving the business environment and increasing productivity with the potential for global competition. (European Court of Auditors, 2022)

Although the Regulation 805/2004 aims to standardize enforcement procedures, variations in national legal systems can still pose challenges. SMEs must deal with different procedural requirements and legal interpretations across Member States. Even practitioners who have gained experience in applying the Regulation 805/2004 criticize the uncertainties in the practical solutions adopted by the courts, the inadequate guidance Member States offer to potential users, and the lack of transparency regarding the national procedural rules that complement the Regulation. The European Commission must proactively include SMEs among the stakeholders when creating the normative text. It is vital to identify the necessary differences.

IV. Conclusion

In the civil and commercial law of the European Union, several steps have been taken towards a "Europe without exequatur", namely: 1) the transformation of the Brussels Convention into Regulation 44/2001, which simplified the procedure for the recognition and enforcement of judgments, 2) Regulation 2201/2003, which abolished the exequatur procedure, first of all for judgments in family disputes, 3) Regulations 805/2004 and 1896/2006, which require the abolition of exequatur in the part of uncontested claims, 4) Regulation 4/2009, which requires its complete elimination in the part of contested claims as well, and 5) Regulation 1215/2012, which abolishes the exequatur procedure in the part of uncontested claims and reduces the formalities in enforcement.

By means of Regulation 805/2004, the decision is certified as a European Enforcement Order for uncontested claims in the Member State of origin and is enforceable in the Member States of the European Union, without the creditor having to obtain a decision on enforcement in the Member State of enforcement or to oppose its recognition. The decision is declared enforceable according to the *lex fori* of the Member State of origin and its content may not be reviewed in the Member State of enforcement (prohibition of revision *au fond*). Its control is allowed only from a purely formal aspect, known in procedural literature as the "rubber-stamp-judgment, stamp without delay procedure" phase. This gives the decision the property of "universal enforceability" and promotes the "fifth freedom of the EU common market" - the free movement of decisions. Accordingly, the European Enforcement Order *par excellence* introduces a new European style in the field of enforcement that has positive reflections on commercial transactions, faster settlement of creditors' claims and better liquidity of small and medium-sized enterprises.

Regulation 805/2004 does not completely abolish exequatur because it does not introduce a unified enforcement procedure at the level of the European Union, nor does it create minimum standards that would be applicable if the national enforcement order is contested in the country of origin.

However, the legal regime of Regulation 805/2004 has a positive impact on the liquidity of small and medium-sized enterprises because it simplifies the manner of enforcement of undisputed commercial claims. This is because the abolition of exequatur is a good step towards a more efficient process of cross-border debt collection. The reduced time and costs associated with debt collection also have a positive impact on the allocation of resources and capacities. The

degree of facilitation of cross-border enforcement of uncontested claims from the perspective of SMEs is also of great importance in terms of improving the liquidity of SMEs by simplifying cross-border debt collection. Since Regulation 805/2004 allows judgments on uncontested claims to be enforced across Member States without the need for mutual recognition procedures, the possibility of late payments from abroad is also reduced. This improves the security of cash flow and allows SMEs to reinvest in their operations, meet their financial obligations and reduce their dependence on external financing. With this very fact, Regulation 805/2004 indirectly strengthens both the financial stability and the competitiveness of SMEs in the internal market of the European Union.

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